

A REVIEW OF ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN MENTAL HEALTH**Dr. Akula Pushpanjali***

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ABSTRACT

AYURVEDA, the ancient Indian system of medicine, offers a sacred approach to mental health that integrates the mind, body and soul. It describes mental health in ***Atharvaveda*** and in subsequent treatises by Charaka, Sushruta & Vagbhata, containing the details of etiology, symptoms, diagnosis, therapy for afflictions in humans and animals. Ayurveda gives prime importance to **positive mental health**. **Grahachikitsa** is one among the eight major branches of Ayurveda that deals with prevention and management of mental problems. Good mental health refers to a perfect linking of emotional, psychological, and social aspects in one's life. A person's mind depends on three qualities like **sattva, rajas, and tamas** in which one's character is modulated, dynamic imbalance of doshas may

upset the mental balance.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Grahachikitsa, Atharvaveda, Mind, Body, Sattva, Raja, Tamas, Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

- **Ayurveda defines as** “Samadoshah samagnishcha, samadhatu malakriyah, Prasannatmendriya manah, svastha ity abhidhiyate”.
- “The one whose “doshas” are balanced, whose metabolism is balanced, whose tissues and eliminations are normal, and whose senses and mind are centered in the Self, is considered healthy and remains full of bliss.”
- Grahachikitsa is one among the eight major branches of Ayurveda that deals with prevention and management of mental problems.
- Good mental health refers to a perfect linking of emotional, psychological, and social

aspects in one's life

- The traditional science of Ayurveda proves the long-term solution to unresolved conditions of mental trauma by rejuvenating physical and psychological factors in one's life.
- Panchakarma course energizes the mind's doshas and mental disturbances through a comprehensive detoxification program and thereby improves mental clarity and mood swings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Mind: According to Ayurveda

- The mind is considered as the launchpad between the senses and the soul. It is an extraordinary organ that controls both sense-related and functional activities of the body.
- It has unique characteristics to correlate with every emotion of life - happiness, fear, anger, shame, contempt, disgust, guilt, distress, interest, surprise, and joy.
- A person's mind depends on three qualities like **sattva, rajas, and tamas** in which one's character is modulated, dynamic imbalance of doshas may upset the mental balance.
- **Marma Training** finds a natural solution to fight negative elements and thereby relieves sleep deprivation, stomach-related issues, and mood swings, hence improving quality of life.

Origins of mental illness

Mental illness occurs due to any sort of brain damage, Stressful life situations, and chronic medical conditions that may lead to various forms of mental health disorders such as OCD, depression, mania, PTSD, and psychosis.

Other Psychiatric conditions in Ayurveda

- i. Unmada (psychosis)
- ii. Apasmara (convulsive disorder)
- iii. Bhrama (illusion)
- iv. Atatvabhinivesham (Obsessive Disorders)
- v. Prajnaparadha (lack of coordination between dhi, dhruti and smruti)
- vi. Tandra (drowsiness)
- vii. Klama (neurasthenia)
- viii. Mada (loss of perception)
- ix. Apatantrakam (hysteria)
- x. Avasada (Depression)

- xi. Citto Udvega (Anxiety neurosis)
- xii. Manasa Mandata (Mental Retardation)
- xiii. Madatyaya (Intoxication etc)

Signs of Mental Health

- 1) Healthy memory
- 2) Awareness of responsibilities
- 3) Following good values
- 4) Self- awareness and responsibilities and beyond self
- 5) Maintaining self-hygiene and cleanliness
- 6) Staying active
- 7) Fearlessness
- 8) Doing things enthusiastically
- 9) Perseverance

Why is Ayurvedic Prevention for Mental Disorders Important?

- Ayurveda's approach to treating any ailments does not include the treatment of any single disease alone.
- Ayurveda follows a therapeutic regime to remove toxins that inhibit the natural energy flow in the body.
- Ayurveda prevention of mental disorders aims at the **relaxation of Ojas** to pacify the conscious mind for better mental and physical health.
- ❖ Certain herbal medications along with their purificatory treatments address the underlying root cause of the mental disorder and are able to find an effective solution for the cause of mental illnesses such as Stress, Migraines, Dementia, Mood swings, Emotional disturbance, and insomnia.
- ❖ Ayurveda seeks realistic behavior of physical and mental health through holistic light to recognize their actual self for mental nourishment.
- ❖ This systematic technique of mindfulness nourishes the brain cells to achieve positive signals that trigger good thoughts, observations, concerns, feelings, and opinions.

Ayurvedic Tips for Enhancing Mental Health

- ✓ Ayurvedic management of mental health brings both Agni and doshas in balance and

enhances a sense of good contentment and well-being.

- ✓ Following a healthy lifestyle with a nutritious diet can relieve signs of mental disorders to a great extent.
- ✓ Also, Ayurveda treatment can calm or relax your body tone in the natural way of the detoxification process.

Diet and Lifestyle Modifications for Mental Health

Ensure we follow a strong **brain-healthy diet** and healthy lifestyle routine to support better mental emotions.

- ❖ Stay hydrated to flush out toxins in your body
- ❖ Avoid high levels of processed food such as fried chips, sugar-filled snacks, and soft drinks.
- ❖ Practice leisure time apart from a busy work schedule
- ❖ Eat seasonal fruits and veggies
- ❖ Enhances the intake of healthy fats for appropriate brain functioning
- ❖ Chew well for better digestion
- ❖ Exercise regularly
- ❖ Have a sound sleep
- ❖ Make a good social connection with friends and family
- ❖ Always consume freshly prepared warm foodstuff
- ❖ Consume food that contains omega-3 fats which are present in oily fish like tuna, salmon, mackerel, perch, herring, and sardines.

Ayurveda Therapies for Enhancing Mental health

In Ayurveda the therapeutics for Mental Illness is divided in to three,

1. Daiva vyapashraya,
2. Yukti vyapashraya,
3. Sattvavajaya Chikitsa

1. DAIVA VYAPRASHRAYA

These methods create self-confidence & pessimistic tendencies. It includes:

- a. **Mantras** (Chanting of Hymns),
- b. **Aushadha** (Sacred Herbs),
- c. **Manimangala** (Auspicious offerings),
- d. Bali,

- e. Upadhan,
- f. Homa (Yajna),
- g. Niyama (Regulations),
- h. Prayascita (Atonement),
- i. Upavasa (Fasting),
- j. Pranipata,
- k. Yatragaman,
- l. Chanting of Mantras, Spiritual, healing, Religious rites etc.

2. YUKTI VYAPRASHRAYA

- It explore the uses of Medicines by two principles i.e Shodhana and Shamana.
- Medicinal Preparations are - Single **Herbs (Medhya Drugs)** - Brahmi, Mandukaparni, Ashwagandha, Jatamamsi, Shankapushpi etc.
- ❖ **Ghritas (Medicated Ghee)** - Panchgavya ghrita, Brahme ghrita, Maha kalyanaka ghrita etc.
- ❖ **Herbomineral Preparations** - Brahme vati, Vata Kulantaka Rasa, Smriti Sagar Rasa, Yogendra rasa, Manasamitra vatakam.

3. SATVAVAJAYA:- (Psychotherapy)

- It aims to control of mind i.e. one should keep himself establish in his oneself after knowing real nature of soul and attaining height of spiritual wisdom.

Its techniques are

- ❖ Gyan - Spiritual Knowledge,
- ❖ Vignana - Educating the Patient,
- ❖ Dhairya - Moral Boosting,
- ❖ Smruti – Reviving the Knowledge,
- ❖ Samadhi - Abstaining from Over indulgence in Materialistic world.

Yoga therapy

- “**Yoga moksho pravarkak**” i.e.by practice of Yoga, One can attain state of Moksha.
- Process of increasing Sattva and decreasing Raja and Tama leading to Karmakshaya (loss of deeds) is way of attaining Moksha

Aachara rasayana

- It's a totally Drug less treatment maintains total life process.
- One who speaks truth, free from anger, abstains from alcohol and over indulgence.
- He maintains Hygiene, regular sleep and wholesome Diet& Controls over his Sense organs etc for Physical, Mental and Spiritual Wellbeing.

Dinacharya

- Beginning the daily habits with awareness, rising with the sun, cleaning the body and beginning our personal practice of worship helps recognize our place in the family, community and cosmos.
- Choosing right foods for our appetite and metabolic needs is a fundamental alignment to show respect of our body and life.
- Right use of time“ means to eat when hungry, rest when fatigued and make time to play for nurturing creativity.
- Circadian rhythms become disturbed by sleeping late, eating stale foods, having sex at a wrong time such as during the menses, with an inappropriate partner or for inappropriate reasons such as self- indulgence.
- Misuse of any of the senses leads to imbalance, as does the misuse of the mind, such as wishing another ill.

Medicated herbs in mental health

Medicated herbs with personalized therapies can calm and relax the mind, body, soul.

- ✓ **Ashwagandha** is one such magical herb to improve cortisol levels& thereby increases the proper functioning of brain cells.
- ✓ **Brahmi** can accelerate positive impact on memory, concentration, and intelligence & helps to reduce the signs of negative emotions .
- ✓ **Turmeric** can improve blood circulation& helps to prevent the brain cells from developing mental disorders.
- **“Virechana”** is a type of panchakarma therapy in which bitter purgative herbs are introduced to induce purgation and thereby cleansing of the body takes place to relieve the stress associated with mental disorders.
- **“Shirodhara”** is the Ayurveda technique of pouring medicated oil onto the center of the forehead and is effective in people who suffer from **insomnia, sleep disorders, anxiety, depression, and other forms of mental disorders.**

□ “**Satvavajaya chikitsa**” induces **positive thoughts** regarding self-awareness, family, and social responsibilities. This therapy is effective in treating **mental disorders** that are caused due to emotional disturbances.

CONCLUSION

- As a whole, Ayurveda can relieve the signs of mental disorders naturally without having any side effects.
- Ayurveda believes & address not only physical body but also the soul or subtle body.
- Ayurvedic principles and treatment guidelines can provide a strong solution to the mental health problems.
- Ayurveda prevents the raising cases of psychiatric illness and mental well being of individuals.

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